

Synthesis of Monoarylidene and Diarylidenethiodiglycollic Acids

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Monoarylidene and diarylidenethiodiglycollic acids have been prepared by the alkoxide catalysed condensations of diethyl thiodiglycollate and aromatic aldehydes; the reaction has been demonstrated to follow a Stobbe mechanistic route.

STOBBE, Ljunggren and Freyberg¹, Hinsberg² and Backer and Stevens³ have reported the formation of a few diarylidenethiodiglycollic acids (I) in the alkoxide catalysed condensation of thiodiglycollic esters with aromatic aldehydes. It has been suggested⁴ that the reaction presumably follows a Stobbe condensation route.

It is observed that under mild conditions of low temperature and short reaction period these condensations yield the diarylidenethiodiglycollic acids (I), and oily acid-esters (II: R=Et) which could be saponified quantitatively to the hitherto unreported monoarylidene-thiodiglycollic acids (II: R=H).

Ethyl α -(3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)-S-carboxymethylthioglycollate (II: Ar=3,4-dimethoxyphenyl; R=Et) m. p. 97° was obtained in the ethoxide catalysed condensation of veratraldehyde and diethyl thiodiglycollate. The analytical values, a single absorption peak at 1695 cm⁻¹ (overlap of cinnamic ester and primary carboxyl carbonyls⁵) and the NMR spectra⁶ (CDCl₃, δ), 6.79-7.83(3H, m, 1, 2, 4-trisubstituted benzene), 4.37 and 1.36 (2H, q and 3H, t, carbethoxymethylene and methyl), 3.88 (6H, s, methoxy), 7.96 (1H, s, olefinic), 3.58 (2H, s, carboxymethylene), 10.72 (1H, s, carboxyl) are all in agreement with the structure of this compound, which would be formed from a δ -lactone intermediate^{4,7} in a Stobbe reaction sequence.

Experimental

Ethyl α -(3, 4-dimethoxybenzylidene)-S-carboxymethylthioglycollate (II: Ar=3, 4-dimethoxyphenyl; R=Et): A mixture of veratraldehyde (16.6 g), diethyl thiodiglycollate (20.6 g) and absolute ethanol (10 ml) was added slowly to a well stirred solution of ethanolic sodium ethoxide [from sodium (4.6 g) and absolute ethanol (100 ml)] at room temperature under inert and anhydrous conditions. Stirring was continued for a further 45 min. and the reaction mixture was acidified

with 6N hydrochloric acid (40 ml). Removal of alcohol under reduced pressure followed by extraction with benzene gave *di*-(3, 4-dimethoxybenzylidene) thiodiglycollic acid (I: Ar=3, 4-dimethoxyphenyl) (2 g), as a highly insoluble compound which could not be crystallised and was purified by washing with ethanol and acetone, m. p. 226° (found: Eq. wt. 221.2; C, 59.43; H, 5.01; S, 7.32%; C₂₂H₁₂O₈S requires eq. wt. 223.0; C, 59.20; H, 4.93; S, 7.17%).

The benzene solution was extracted with cold aqueous sodium carbonate and the alkaline phase on acidification gave ethyl α -(3, 4-dimethoxybenzylidene)-S-carboxymethylthioglycollate (II: Ar=3, 4-dimethoxyphenyl, R=Et), (20.5 g), crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (60°-80°), m.p. 97°, (found: Eq. wt. 325.4; C, 55.50; H, 5.59; S, 9.68%; C₁₈H₁₈O₈S requires eq. wt. 326; C, 55.22; H, 5.52; S, 9.81%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 334 nm (log ϵ 4.1).

α -(3, 4-Dimethoxybenzylidene)thiodiglycollic acid (II: Ar=3, 4-dimethoxyphenyl; R=H)

Ethyl α -(3, 4-dimethoxybenzylidene)-S-carboxymethylthioglycollate (1 g) was refluxed for 4 hr. with 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide (15 ml). The reaction mixture on acidification yielded 3, 4-dimethoxybenzylidenethiodiglycollic acid (II: Ar=3, 4-dimethoxyphenyl; R=H), (0.8 g), crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 222°-4° (found: Eq. wt. 148.4; C, 52.62; H, 4.29; S, 10.40%; C₁₃H₁₄O₆S requires eq. wt. 149; C, 52.34; H, 4.69; S, 10.17%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 308 nm (log ϵ 4.46).

Ethoxide Catalysed Condensation of Diethyl thiodiglycollate and Aromatic Aldehydes:

Benzylidenethiodiglycollic acid (II: Ar=phenyl; R=H): To a well stirred solution of ethanolic sodium ethoxide [from sodium (6.9 g) and absolute ethanol (150 ml)] was added a mixture of benzaldehyde (15.9 g) and diethyl thiodiglycollate (30.9 g) at room temperature under inert and anhydrous conditions. After 45 min. of stirring the reaction mixture was acidified with cold 6N hydrochloric acid (60 ml.) and the alcohol was removed under reduced pressure. Extraction of the

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residue with benzene afforded dibenzylidenethiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar=phenyl) (3.5 g) as an insoluble compound, crystallised from hot methanol, m. p. 218° (lit.¹ m. p. 185°-8°); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 272 nm (log ϵ 4.09), IR (carbonyl) : 1684 cm^{-1} (cinnamic acid⁵).

The benzene solution was extracted with cold aqueous sodium carbonate. The alkaline layer on acidification afforded an oil (33.9 g) which could not be crystallised [found : Eq. wt. 264.1 ; Ester-acid (II : Ar = Ph ; R = Et) ; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 266]. This oil (1 g) on refluxing with 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml) followed by acidification yielded benzylidenethiodiglycollic acid (II : Ar = phenyl ; R = H) (0.8 g), crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 162° (found : Eq. wt. 120.1 ; C, 55.30 ; H, 4.32 ; S, 13.21% ; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 119.0 ; C, 55.46 ; H, 4.20 ; S, 13.45%) ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 281 nm (log ϵ 3.74).

Similarly piperonal gave dipiperonylidene-thiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar = 3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl) purified by washing with alcohol and acetone, m. p. 243° (found : Eq. wt. 206.2 ; C, 57.79 ; H, 3.41 ; S, 7.62% ; $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_8\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 207.0 ; C, 57.97 ; H, 3.38 ; S, 7.72%) ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 317 nm (log ϵ 4.15) and oily acid-ester [(II : Ar = 3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl ; R = Et) (found : Eq. wt. 303 ; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_8\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 310)] which was saponified to get piperonylidene-thiodiglycollic acid (II : Ar = 3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl R = H), crystallised from methanol, m. p. 198° (found : Eq. wt. 141.6 ; C, 50.80 ; H, 3.56 ; S, 11.53% ; $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 141.0 ; C, 51.07 ; H, 3.54 ; S, 11.34% ; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 323 nm (log ϵ 4.35).

p-Chlorobenzaldehyde gave di-(*p*-chlorobenzylidene)-thiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl) purified washing with alcohol and acetone, m. p. 268° (found : Eq. wt. 197.2 ; C, 54.30 ; H, 3.16 ; S, 8.01% ; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 197.5 ; C, 54.69 ; H, 3.03, S, 8.10%) and oily acid-ester (II : Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl R = Et) (found : Eq. wt. 297, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClO}_4\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 300.5). This oil on saponification gave *p*-chlorobenzylidenethiodiglycollic acid, (II : Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl, R = H) crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 213° (found : Eq. wt. 136.1, C, 48.29 ; H, 3.33, S, 14.51% ; $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ClO}_4\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 136.25, C, 48.44 ; H, 3.30 ; S, 14.79%)

From *p*-, *o*- and *m*-methoxybenzaldehydes and *o*- and *m*-chlorobenzaldehydes only the diarylidene-thiodiglycollic acids could be isolated in a crystalline form.

Thus anisaldehyde gave di-(*p*-methoxybenzylidene)-thiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar = *p*-methoxyphenyl) crystallised from hot ethanol, m. p. 158° (found : Eq. wt. 194.2 ; C, 62.29 ; H, 4.27 ; S, 8.32% ; $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 193.0 ; C, 62.18, H, 4.66, S, 8.29%).

o-Methoxybenzaldehyde gave di-(*o*-methoxybenzylidene)-thiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar = *o*-methoxyphenyl), crystallised from methanol, m. p. 219° (found : Eq. wt. 192.6 ; C, 62.30 ; H, 4.60 ; S, 8.29% ; $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 193.0 ; C, 62.18, H, 4.66 ; S, 8.29%).

m-Methoxybenzaldehyde gave di-(*m*-methoxybenzylidene)-thiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar = *m*-methoxyphenyl) crystallised from hot ethanol, m. p. 174° (found : Eq. wt. 193.2 ; C, 62.12 ; H, 4.57 ; S, 8.18% ; $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 193 ; C, 62.18 ; H, 4.66 ; S, 8.29%).

o-Chlorobenzaldehyde gave di-(*o*-chlorobenzylidene)-thiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar = *o*-chlorophenyl), crystallised from hot ethanol, m. p. 252° (found : Eq. wt. 196.1 ; C, 54.44 ; H, 2.73 ; S, 7.65% ; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 197.5 ; C, 54.69 ; H, 3.03 ; S, 8.10%).

m-Chlorobenzaldehyde gave di-(*m*-chlorobenzylidene)-thiodiglycollic acid (I : Ar = *m*-chlorophenyl), crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 231° (found : Eq. wt. 197.1 ; C, 54.76 ; H, 3.16 ; S, 8.32% ; $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires eq. wt. 197.5 ; C, 54.69 ; H, 3.03 ; S, 8.10%).

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References

1. H. STOBBER, G. LJUNGREN and J. FREYBERG, *Ber.*, 1926, 59B, 265.
2. O. HINSBERG, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1911, 84, 192.
3. H. J. BACKER and W. STEVENS, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1940, 59, 423.
4. W. S. JOHNSON and G. H. DAUB, "Organic Reactions", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1951, Vol. VI, p. 20.
5. K. RAGHAVA RAO and G. BAGAVANT, *Current Sci.*, 1969, 38, 90.
6. S. F. DYKE, A. J. FLOYD, M. SAINSBURY and R. S. THEOBALD, "Organic Spectroscopy, An Introduction", Penguin Books Ltd., England, 1971, pp. 143, 153, 214, 220.
7. H. WYNBERG and H. J. KOOREMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 1739.